

Notes about spectrum and linewidth

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Here I briefly overview some basics ideas about spectrum of some cavity field.

I. FILTER CAVITY AND SPECTRUM VIA TWO-TIME CORRELATION

Following [1], spectrum of some field \hat{a} can be determined with the help of additional *filter cavity* weakly coupled to the main cavity. The Hamiltonian of the filter cavity (in frame co-rotating with the main cavity rotating frame) is

$$\hat{\mathcal{H}}_f = \hbar(\delta_f \hat{f}^+ \hat{f} + G(\hat{a}^+ \hat{f} + \hat{a} \hat{f}^+)), \quad (1)$$

and there is additional relaxation term

$$\hat{\mathcal{L}}_f[\hat{\rho}] = -\frac{\beta}{2} \left(\hat{f}^+ \hat{f} \hat{\rho} + \hat{\rho} \hat{f}^+ \hat{f} - 2\hat{f} \hat{\rho} \hat{f}^+ \right), \quad (2)$$

where coupling strength G and decay rate β are supposed to be extremely small. Then the equations for operators \hat{f} and \hat{f}^+ are:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\hat{f}}{dt} &= \frac{i}{\hbar} [\hat{\mathcal{H}}_f, \hat{f}] - \frac{\beta}{2} \left(\hat{f}^+ \hat{f} \hat{f} + \hat{f} \hat{f}^+ \hat{f} - 2\hat{f}^+ \hat{f} \hat{f} \right) + \hat{F}_f \\ &= -i\delta_f \hat{f} - iG\hat{a} - \frac{\beta}{2} \hat{f} + \hat{F}_f. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{d\hat{f}^+}{dt} = i\delta_f \hat{f}^+ + iG\hat{a}^+ - \frac{\beta}{2} \hat{f}^+ + \hat{F}_{f^+}. \quad (4)$$

We can write the solutions of these equations as

$$\hat{f}(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t e^{-(\frac{\beta}{2} + i\delta_f)(t-t')} \left(-iG\hat{a}(t') + \hat{F}_f(t') \right) dt' \quad (5)$$

$$\hat{f}^+(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t e^{-(\frac{\beta}{2} - i\delta_f)(t-t')} \left(iG\hat{a}^+(t'') + \hat{F}_{f^+}(t'') \right) dt'' \quad (6)$$

therefore, average number of photons in the filter cavity is

$$\langle \hat{f}^+(t) \hat{f}(t) \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^t \int_{-\infty}^t e^{-\frac{\beta}{2}(2t-t'-t'')} e^{i\delta_f(t'-t'')} \left(G^2 \langle \hat{a}^+(t'') \hat{a}(t') \rangle + \langle \hat{F}_{f^+}(t'') \hat{F}_f(t') \rangle \right) dt' dt'' \quad (7)$$

Note that $\langle \hat{F}_{f^+}(t'') \hat{F}_f(t') \rangle = 0$. In stationary regime one may take $t = 0$, and introduce

$$R(\tau) = \langle \hat{a}^+(t + \tau) \hat{a}(t) \rangle \quad \tau = t'' - t' \quad T = -\frac{t' + t''}{2} \quad (8)$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{-\infty}^0 \int_{-\infty}^0 F(t', t'') dt' dt'' &= \int_0^{\infty} \int_{-2T}^{2T} F\left(-T + \frac{\tau}{2}, -T - \frac{\tau}{2}\right) d\tau dT \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{|\tau|/2}^{\infty} F\left(-T + \frac{\tau}{2}, -T - \frac{\tau}{2}\right) dT d\tau. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Using 9, the fact that β is small (in comparison with decay rate of 2-time correlation function $R(\tau)$), and using $R(\tau) = R^*(-\tau)$, we can rewrite (7) as

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \hat{f}^+(0) \hat{f}(0) \rangle &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\int_{|\tau|/2}^{\infty} e^{-\beta T} dT \right] e^{-i\delta_f \tau} G^2 R(\tau) d\tau = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\exp[-\beta|\tau|/2]}{\beta} e^{-i\delta_f \tau} G^2 R(\tau) d\tau \\ &\approx \frac{G^2}{\beta} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-i\delta_f \tau} R(\tau) d\tau = \frac{G^2}{\beta} \int_0^{\infty} R(\tau) e^{-i\delta_f \tau} d\tau + \frac{G^2}{\beta} \int_0^{\infty} R^*(\tau) e^{i\delta_f \tau} d\tau \\ &= \frac{2G^2}{\beta} \text{Re} \left\{ \int_0^{\infty} R(\tau) e^{-i\delta_f \tau} d\tau \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

II. CALCULATION OF 2-TIME CORRELATION FUNCTION VIA QUANTUM REGRESSION THEOREM

Consider, for the sake of simplicity, full system, including both system and bath. Let $\hat{\mathcal{H}}$ be the Hamiltonian of this system. Then, using Heisengerg representation, we get

$$\langle \hat{a}(t) \hat{b}(0) \rangle = \text{Tr} \left[e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \hat{\mathcal{H}} t} \hat{a}(0) e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} \hat{\mathcal{H}} t} \hat{b}(0) \hat{\rho}(0) \right]$$

then we use the cyclic property of Trace:

$$= \text{Tr} \left[\hat{a}(0) e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} \hat{\mathcal{H}} t} \hat{b}(0) \hat{\rho}(0) e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \hat{\mathcal{H}} t} \right].$$

Introducing “fictional” density matrix $\hat{\rho}'$ such, that

$$\hat{\rho}'(0) = \hat{b}(0) \hat{\rho}(0)$$

we get

$$\langle \hat{a}(t) \hat{b}(0) \rangle = \text{Tr} \left[\hat{a}(0) e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} \hat{\mathcal{H}} t} \hat{\rho}'(0) e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \hat{\mathcal{H}} t} \right] = \text{Tr} [\hat{a}(0) \hat{\rho}'(t)].$$

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- [1] K. Debnath, Y. Zhang, and K. Mølmer, Phys. Rev. A **98**, 063837 (2018), URL <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevA.98.063837>.